

Using Large Language Models to assess Digital Readiness of a Higher Education Institution

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Abstract

Measuring the Digital Readiness of a Higher Education Institution (HEI) is an important step in the process of achieving institutional digital maturity. While most often the digital readiness is measured using surveys answered by stakeholders, a new approach, proposed by the DigiReady+ framework, is to use institutional data, following a data-driven approach, that allows for more objective and evidence-based assessment. In the process of implementing such an approach, we identified two kinds of dimensions of digital readiness that need to be measured, i.e., those that can be based on quantitative institutional data and those that are of more qualitative nature. Examples of the first are the Digital Infrastructure, Digital Teaching, and Learning, etc., while examples of the latter refer to Leadership, Government, Strategy and Policies. The level of readiness for the second kind of dimensions is based usually on institutional documents, that are not necessarily widely known. In this study we attempted to automate the process of assessing these dimensions, using Large Language Models. Interesting results are reported that can lead to automating the process and integrating these techniques in the data-driven measurement of HEI's digital readiness.

1 Introduction

The *Digital Readiness* of an organization, like most composite indicators (OECD et al., 2008), can be assessed through measurements of several key dimensions (Alzahova et al. 2020). According to the DigiReady+ framework (Tsimpanis et al., 2023), that concerns the Digital Readiness of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), the seven dimensions that compose it are: D1. Digital Leadership and Government, D2. Digital Strategy and Policies, D3. Teaching and Learning, D4. Content and Curricula, D5. Training and Support, D6. Infrastructure, D7. Networks and Collaboration. Each one of these dimensions is decomposed in specific topics and indicators. These have been defined through participatory workshops involving key stakeholders. From these dimensions, the first two, i.e., the vision of the HEI Digital Leadership and Government (D1) as well as the Digital Policies and Strategies (D2) that are implemented by institutional authorities are of the utmost significance for digital readiness.

These dimensions highlight leadership’s commitment to using digital technologies to enhance processes and activities, speeding up the effective achievement of organization’s goals. They also cover indicators related to quality, accessibility, and legal aspects. In addition, the existence of clearly defined policies and strategies about digitization and digital transformation is of great value when measuring the digital readiness of a HEI. The policies and strategies function as guiding framework for optimally utilizing digital tools to augment diverse aspects, such as teaching, learning, research, and administrative procedures, while hold a crucial responsibility in protecting the university from potential hazards associated with the process of digital transformation, including but not limited to data breaches and cyber-attacks, while also ensuring adherence to relevant laws and regulations.

In the context of implementing a quantitative approach for measuring digital readiness in European universities, we investigated the use of available Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools, based on Large Language Models (Vaswani et al., 2017; Zhu et al., 2024), that can assess such qualitative indicators. In recent years a few such tools have been made publicly available and have been used in several domains (Bubeck et al., 2023). However, such systems have limitations, like response accuracy (a term used is “AI hallucinations”) and limited coverage of up-to-date knowledge due to constrains of model training. A particular new trend that attempts to tackle these limitations, most relevant to our task, is the combination of web search engines and large language models, an approach also known as Retrieval-Augmented Generation, see (Lewis et al., 2020; Gao et al., 2024; Vu et al., 2023). The concept is summarized in figure 1.

Figure 1: Augmenting search engines with large language models.

As discussed in the next section, we identified publicly available tools, that are implementing this approach, and selected the one that meets the requirements of our problem, and then we proceeded with answering the following research questions, relating to assessment of digital readiness:

- RQ1. Is it possible, using existing Large Language Model tools, to assess key indicators of the digital readiness framework, with focus on dimensions D1 and D2?

- RQ2. Can such LLM-based models provide adequate supporting evidence of their assessment?
- RQ3 Can the assessment of the indicators be quantified and included in the overall methodology and tools built for assessing digital readiness of the Higher Education Institution?

In the following we describe a study involving the University of Patras, University of Duisburg-Essen, and the University of Valladolid, that attempts to provide responses to the above research questions, with main focus to RQ1 and RQ2.

2 Methodology of the study and tools selection

The first step in our study was to define the LLM tool to be used and the methodology to be followed. The tools considered are shown in Table 1. From these tools, Perplexity¹, You², and Microsoft Copilot³ are LLM enhanced search engines, while ChatGPT⁴ and Google Bard⁵ are more traditional LLMs included for comparison. Criteria for selecting a suitable LLM included public availability, evidence provision through sources as well as displaying additional sources. To select a suitable LLM tool, we tested the performance of the tools of Table 1 on the same task, relating to digital readiness, i.e. examined which one provided the most comprehensive answer with relevant sources. We used a university of an English-speaking country as we expected that relevant sources would be in English. The test question was: ‘Does Brunel University have a digital transformation strategy?’. We used the tools of Table 1, in November 2023. *ChatGPT* did not provide an answer, *Google Bard*, now called Gemini, stated information for the HEI by citing three sources but did not provide an answer to the question. MS Copilot showcased Brunel University’s digital research and innovation with three university-related sources but did not directly answer if the university has a digital transformation strategy. ‘You’ could not determine if the HEI had a digital transformation strategy and referred to Brunel’s Institute of Digital Futures, supplying one source. Finally, *Perplexity.ai* replied that there is a digital transformation strategy by linking it to the student experience strategy involving digital teaching.

Tool	Answered Q1 with Sources	Number of sources
Perplexity	Yes	5
Chat-GPT v4	No	0
Google Bard	No	0
You	Yes	1
MS Copilot	Yes	3

Table 1: Candidate tools to be used in the study

From the results in Table 1, *Perplexity.ai*, *MS Copilot*, and ‘You’ provided five, three, and one sources respectively. *Perplexity.ai*’s response, while lacking a direct reference to a strategy document, was the most complete and well-referenced, finding related sources on Brunel University’s digital transformation. Without knowledge of Brunel’s ground truth and the sources used by the LLM tools, assessing accuracy is challenging. However, based on this initial test, we decided to proceed with using *Perplexity.ai* for the remainder of the study, as the obtained reply was more thorough and relevant.

Perplexity.ai is an AI-driven search engine that answers user queries using evidence from various web sources. It is powered by OpenAI GPT-3.5/4.0 and integrated with Microsoft’s Bing. Users

¹ <https://www.perplexity.ai/>

² <https://you.com/>

³ <https://copilot.microsoft.com/>

⁴ <https://chat.openai.com/>

⁵ <https://bard.google.com/chat>

can ask follow-up questions, and it responds contextually, citing sources in the reply. One unique feature is the Copilot, which offers guided AI search, particularly useful for complex questions.

To obtain quality responses, we have honed a method through repeated trials with the LLM – search engine Perplexity.ai to extract data and gauge metrics relevant to the first two dimensions of the DigiReady+ framework. Our approach involves a three-step process: (a) starting with the generation of an initial question prompt, then (b) critiquing these prompts by examining their specific properties, and ultimately (c) evaluating the responses provided by the LLM – search engine. We have carefully accounted for a variety of attributes such as subtleties in language, the extent and structure of the questions, as well as question size, format, and terminology variations during the formulation of these processes.

First, we formulate an initial question prompt for each indicator by consulting the DigiReady+ framework to identify key terms and expected response types. Next, we translate these terms into the institution's native language for accuracy. We assess the quality of the native language question prompt, ensuring precision and considering potential shifts in meaning across languages. If needed, we edit the prompt to accurately capture the indicator's essence. This concludes the first step, after which we proceed to assess the question prompt characteristics. In the second step, we verify that our question prompt meets specific requirements. Experimental trials have shown that question size and format are crucial. We assess if the prompt is concise, as focused queries with key elements yield more reliable responses. Structuring prompts as questions, rather than statements, also improves responses. Once we confirm adherence to these guidelines, we pose the question to the LLM-search engine and proceed to the final step of evaluating the generated answer.

In the third step, we evaluate the LLM-search engine responses. If the answer meets expectations with sufficient evidence, we collect it and conclude the process. If unsatisfactory, we ask a follow-up question. If the response improves, we collect evidence and finish. If not, we restart the process from the first step, adjusting the question prompt as needed. If improvement remains elusive after multiple attempts, this method does not yield evidence.

To assess the LLM-search engine's implementation, we review collected evidence, generated replies, and sources. The sources are evaluated based on the following requirements. **The source exists**, is available for public view and it does not correspond to an LLM hallucination. **The source applies to the institution**, is related to, or mentions in its information the HEI we are investigating. **The source is relevant to the question**, where the information is relevant to the institution we are investigating and contains relevant information for the given question. We prioritize cited sources referenced in the reply as evidence during the evaluation.

We assess the generated answer against ground truth data. It is deemed *accurate* if it provides a well-constructed, reliable response based on available public information. If it contains accurate elements but includes not-verified main points or assumptions, it is considered *partly accurate*. An *inaccurate* answer contains incorrect information sourced from unrelated content, including hallucinated details, lacks referenced sources, and does not relate to the question prompt.

3 Implementation of this approach in European Universities

In this section, we describe the implementation of using *Perplexity.ai*, a search engine powered by LLM, for assessing DigiReady+ indicators involved in dimensions D1. Digital Leadership and Government, and D2. Digital Strategy and Policies, in the case of three prominent European universities. Specifically, the implementation study included the University of Patras, the University of Duisburg-Essen, and the University of Valladolid.

In most cases, we expect that the associated information and documents should be publicly available, as an example, regarding indicator D1.2 - *Existence of a Digital Transformation Strategy*, the

HEI should have made public the document of digital transformation strategy. That was the case for 26 out of 33 indicators. For each indicator we created question prompts and follow-up questions, using the methodology outlined in section 2. Then the evaluators from each University implemented and evaluated the answers based on the ground truth and the corresponding sources.

For example, for indicator D2.11 ‘Governance and accountability of digital strategy’, it involves having a governance framework overseeing the HEI’s digital strategy. The question prompt was “Does the [Name of University] have a unit that oversees the implementation of its digital transformation?” in the native languages of each University (Table 2).

University of Patras	University of Duisburg-Essen	University of Valladolid
Έχει το Πανεπιστήμιο Πατρών μονάδα που επιβλέπει την υλοποίηση του ψηφιακού μετασχηματισμού του;	Gibt es an der Universität Duisburg-Essen eine Stelle, die die Umsetzung der digitalen Transformation begleitet?	¿ Dispone la Universidad de Valladolid de una unidad que supervise la implantación de su transformación digital?

Table 2: Question prompts for indicator D2.11 for each university.

3.1 Examples of evaluating the implementation of this approach in specific indicators

In this section, we showcase the proposed approach using *Perplexity.ai* to measure two indicators across three HEIs. We aim to show both the strengths and potential limitations of using an LLM – search engine for assessing a university’s digital readiness.

The implementation of this approach for the indicator **D2.11 ‘Governance and accountability of digital strategy’**, each evaluator used the question prompts in Table 2.

Regarding the University of Patras, Perplexity AI provided the following answer, translated from Greek to English, “*Yes, the University of Patras has a unit that oversees the implementation of digital transformation. This is the Operational Quality Management Unit (OQMU), which is responsible for monitoring the progress of the implementation of the digital transformation plans, among other activities[1]⁶. In addition, the Directorate of Digital Governance and Information and Communication Technologies is responsible for the implementation of the digital transformation plan of the University of Patras [2].*”

In the answer the LLM states that the University of Patras has a unit responsible for overseeing the implementation of its digital transformation, which is the Quality Management Unit. It also states the governance structure responsible for implementing it. The statement is qualified by the first source, that is the official webpage for the Operational Management Unit, that states that one of its responsibilities is to “*monitoring progress in the implementation of the plans for digital transformation, equal access for people with disabilities and people with special educational needs and sustainable development*”. The LLM tool also states the responsible team for the implementation of University of Patras digital transformation strategy, providing the official webpage of the unit, where it is stated that one of its responsibilities is “*the operational planning, promotion, support and monitoring of the implementation of e-government and the Digital Transformation Paper in the areas related to the HEI.*” and “*the implementation of the digital transformation plan of the HEI.*”. So, the LLM – powered search engine provided an **accurate answer** to the question and the cited sources are both related to the University of Patras and are relevant to the question.

Regarding the University of Duisburg-Essen, Perplexity AI provided the following answer, translated from German to English, “*Yes, there is an office at the University of Duisburg-Essen that supports the implementation of the digital transformation. The Department of Digital Transformation and Academic*

⁶ [N]: Referenced source from *perplexity.ai* that is provided in the generated answer.

Controlling (DTAC) sees itself as a modern service provider in all matters relating to the digital transformation of administrative support processes. It supports and coordinates the implementation of the NRW E-Government Act, the Online Access Act and the Single Digital Gateway Regulation. Furthermore, the DTAC department initiates, coordinates, and supports the necessary changes at the University of Duisburg-Essen that are based on digital technologies [1]. In addition, there are various degree programs and courses at the University of Duisburg-Essen that deal with digital transformation. These include the master's program "Digital Business Innovation and Transformation"[4][5][7] and the course "Digital Business Leadership"[2]. Both programmes deal with the planning, organization and management of the digital transformation of organizations. In addition, the University of Duisburg-Essen also has the "Digital Communication and Transformation"[3] department, which deals with digital transformation and communication."

The response of the language model is **partially correct**. Indeed, UDE has established the unit DTAC (Digital Transformation and Academic Control) that aims to support the university in strategic decisions regarding the digital transformation of the UDE's administrative support processes. However, the second part of the response is incorrect and not relevant to the question. It seems that the model is using outdated information about the university's curricula that do not represent the current situation or reflect the work processes of the HEI to promote digital transformation.

Regarding the University of Valladolid, *Perplexity.ai* provided the following answer, translated from Spanish to English "Yes, the University of Valladolid has a unit that oversees the implementation of its digital transformation. This is the Vice-Rectorate for Teaching Innovation and Digital Transformation, which is articulated on the administrative units Audiovisual UVa, VirtUVa Center and the Service for Information Technology and Communications (STIC). This vice-rectorate focuses on supporting the development of online teaching, training in digital skills, improving ICT services and technological infrastructures, enhancing digital content and technological evolution of the management processes [1]. It is also responsible for managing the development of projects of the University of Valladolid within the framework of the Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Plan[1]."

The response provided by the LLM tool is quite accurate, and it can be considered **correct** and relevant to the question. It correctly identifies the unit (Vice Rectorate of Digital Transformation) that oversees the definition and implementation of digital transformation of this HEI. Moreover, it almost uses the literal main text at this unit's website. It is also noteworthy that the response does not cite all five sources shown in the reference list. Three out of five sources are valid, and indeed the official HEI YouTube video on digital transformation is probably the clearest formulation of the ways that this unit oversees and implements the digital transformation of the institution. However, the remaining two sources are irrelevant since they either refer to another university or to generic dissemination video of a consulting company.

A second example concerns employment of this method for the indicator **D1.2 'Existence of a Digital Transformation Strategy'** where the indicator is related to the development of the institution's strategy for its digital transformation. To answer the indicator, the same question prompt was created for all Universities "Has the [Name of University] created a strategy for its digital transformation?" to find the digital transformation document of each HEI if it is available for the public for each involved University (Table 3).

University of Patras	University of Duisburg-Essen	University of Valladolid
Έχει δημιουργήσει το Πανεπιστήμιο Πατρών μια στρατηγική για τον ψηφιακό μετασχηματισμό του;	Hat die Universität Duisburg-Essen eine Strategie für ihre digitale Transformation entwickelt?	¿Tiene la Universidad de Valladolid una estrategia clara de transformación digital?

Table 3: Question prompts for D1.2 for each University.

In relation to the University of Patras, the tool provided the following answer, translated from Greek to English, “*The University of Patras has developed a strategy for its digital transformation. The university's Digital Governance and Information and Communication Technologies Directorate has set operational objectives that include digital governance within the institution, the use of information and communication technologies, the development and management of information and telecommunication networks and systems, as well as digital transparency and the provision of open data [1]. In addition, the University's Quality Management Functional Unit is responsible for organising, coordinating, and monitoring the implementation of the digital transformation strategic plan, as well as monitoring the progress of the digital transformation plans [2]. Therefore, through these structures and actions, the University of Patras has undertaken a comprehensive effort to enhance its digital transformation, covering aspects such as digital governance, the use of information and communication technologies, as well as the development of digital skills [1][2].*”

The LLM states clearly that the HEI has developed a strategy for its digital transformation, and it continues by explaining the units’ responsible for developing and overseeing the digital transformation strategy. The cited sources are the official webpages for the units that are provided by the HEI, were they state those responsibilities. However, in neither of these sources the University of Patras has developed a clear digital transformation strategy. So, to further examine this statement a follow-up question was conducted, “*Can you describe the objectives of the strategy?*”

For the follow-up question, it gave the following answer, “*According to the search results, no specific source was found that describes the objectives of the University of Patras' digital transformation strategy. However, from the results found, it appears that this strategy includes the use of information and communication technologies, the development and management of information and telecommunication networks and systems, as well as digital transparency and the provision of open data [1]. In addition, the university's Quality Management Functional Unit has responsibilities that include coordinating the implementation of the strategic plan and programmatic planning agreements for digital transformation, as well as monitoring the progress of the digital transformation plan [3].*”

It corrects its answer by stating that no specific source was found that describes the objectives of the HEI digital transformation strategy. However, it continues by stating some objectives the strategy includes, by referencing a source nor relating to University of Patras nor any other HEI. At the end it gave the same information for the responsible units as in the previous answer.

It’s apparent that the LLM cannot provide a straight short answer that states that didn’t find any sources regarding the question. Since it assumed that the HEI had developed a digital transformation strategy since it has assigned units to plan and monitor the digital transformation plan. However, when it was asked specifically for the digital transformation plan it admitted that it didn’t find any sources and next quoted objectives from an unrelated source, repeating the previously provided information.

Concerning the University of Duisburg-Essen the tool generated the following answer, “*The University of Duisburg-Essen has developed strategies as part of the digital transformation. Workshops were held with members of top management to discuss the strategic implications of digital transformation in higher education [1]. In addition, the university is addressing the topic of ‘Digital Transformation and IS/IT Innovation Management’ and is researching digital business strategies as well as guidelines for IT innovation management [5]. Although the specific action plan is not publicly available, these activities indicate that the University of Duisburg-Essen is actively involved in developing and implementing strategies for its digital transformation.*”

The response is **partially correct** and answers the question to some extent. UDE has developed a digitalization strategy for studying and teaching which is publicly available as part of its efforts to promote digital transformation. Nonetheless, the follow-up details regarding Digital Transformation and IS/IT Innovation Management refer to curricula of the university that are not relevant to the university’s strategic planning.

Regarding the University of Valladolid, the tool provided the following answer, “*The University of Valladolid has been working on digital transformation initiatives. A project has been carried out to adapt in an innovative and agile way to the new digital coordinates imposed by today's society, strengthening the culture of transparency and open government in all its spheres [2]. In addition, the university has hosted the 47th CRUE Digitalization Conference, which indicates an interest in and commitment to digitalization [3][4]. Although no document detailing a clear digital transformation strategy for the University of Valladolid has been found, these indications suggest that the institution is actively involved in digital transformation processes.*”.

The answer provided is **partially correct**. On the one hand, two of the five cited web resources are not valid, since one resource refers to the digital transformation plan of another university, while the second one refers to the smart city strategy of the Valladolid City Council. On the other hand, the remaining three cited web resources are mostly valid. One of them refers to the HEI's specific and concrete open data and transparency plan that is indeed based on digital technologies, although it covers a partial facet of digital strategy. Another cited web source deals with a rather minor fact, since it simply refers to the 2023 Spanish conference of HEI rectors on digital transformation, that may suggest an additional interest of the leadership team on digital transformation, but not necessarily the existence of a clear strategic plan. Finally, the most reliable cited web source corresponds to the website of the dedicated Vice Rectorate on Digital Transformation that has been recently created. This website is a valuable source since it is the main hub for all related information on digital transformation. The answer indeed almost literally includes the main statement of the website, in which a rather vague institutional position is formulated. However, the overall strong statement provided by Perplexity AI cannot be justified by the cited resources, although the answer is partially supported by valid information. Overall, the response is only partially valid, given that there does not exist a coherent and explicit strategy of digital transformation at this HEI.

3.2 Assessment of implementation of this approach

In this section, from the implementation of UPAT, UDE and Uva we will present the distribution of the answer's accuracy, the percent of acceptable answers, i.e. the answers that were evaluated as accurate and partly accurate, the percentage of the sources that existed and the percentage of the reliable sources, i.e. the sources that applied to the HEI and were relevant to the question.

For the *University of Patras*, the tool provided **7** accurate answers, **8** partially accurate answers and **4** inaccurate answers. For D1, for the eleven indicators we examined, **72%** are acceptable answers. For D2, for the seven indicators we examined, **87.5%** are acceptable. Analyzing UPAT's answers, *perplexity.ai* used 46 out of 158 sources for evidence in D1's answers. From the cited sources that were used as evidence in the generated answers, for D1 indicators, 95% of those existed and 57% were reliable sources. For the D2 answers it analyzed 99 sources where only 22 were used as evidence. For the cited sources in D2 answers, all the sources existed and 54% were reliable sources.

For the *University of Duisburg-Essen*, the AI tool provided **3** accurate answers, **12** partially accurate answers and **4** inaccurate answers. For the **D1**, **72%** of the answers are **acceptable**. For **D2**, **87.5%** are acceptable answers. Analyzing UDE's answers, for D1's answers 22 out of 66 sources were used as evidence. From the cited sources, for D1 answers, all of those existed and 50% were reliable sources. For the D2 answers it analyzed 132 sources where only 43 were used as evidence. For cited sources in D2 answers, all the sources existed and 37% were reliable sources.

For the University of Valladolid, the AI tool provided **6** accurate answers, **8** partially accurate answers and **5** inaccurate answers. For D1, **63%** of the answers are **acceptable**. For **D2**, for the seven indicators we examined **87.5%** are acceptable answers.

Analyzing Uva's answers, for D1 48 out of 81 sources were used as evidence. From the cited sources, for D1 answers, 88% of those existed and 77% were reliable sources. For D2 it analyzed 36 sources where only 23 were used as evidence. For the cited sources in D2, 88% of sources existed and 83% were reliable.

To measure overall accuracy, we assigned a value of 1 to accurate answers, 0.5 to partially accurate, and 0 to inaccurate. The average accuracy for D1 at UPAT is 0.5, UDE is 0.5, and Uva is 0.45. For D2, the average accuracy at UPAT is 0.68, UDE is 0.43, and Uva is 0.62. The most accurate indicators from the implementation across all HEIs were D1.1 (acc=0.83), D1.3 (acc=0.66), D1.9 (acc=1), D2.1 (acc=0.83), D2.6 (acc=0.83), and D2.11 (acc=0.83). The indicators D1.4, D1.5, D1.7, D2.3 and D2.12 were inaccurate with accuracy less than 0.33. Eight indicators had accuracy 0.5. So, for the remaining 14 indicators with accuracy greater than 0.5, we can assume that this method can be used to propose information for measuring them.

4 Discussion

We employed *perplexity.ai* to assess DigiReady+ indicators in dimensions D1 and D2 across three European universities, University of Patras, University of Duisburg-Essen, and University of Valladolid. We evaluated the generated answers for accuracy against ground truth and the provided sources, we assessed 19 indicators in total, 11 from D1 and 8 from D2. We analyze here the answers' accuracy distribution, average accuracy, and the distribution of cited sources relevant to the HEIs and the questions to answer our research questions.

From the average accuracy of all HEIs indicator's resources, we can determine for which of the tested indicators reliable information can be found to measure them. Reliable information will be considered an answer with average accuracy > 0.5, for D1 we can find reliable information to measure **8** out of the **11** tested indicators and for D2 **6** out of the **8** indicators. In total, **14** out of the **19** indicators can be measured reliably with this implementation. Therefore, it is possible to assess key indicators of the digital readiness framework, with focus on dimensions D1 and D2 using an LLM -search engine.

Overall, across the three HEIs, 60% of cited sources were relevant to the university and the question. For highly accurate answers (accuracy > 0.66), 75% of sources were reliable, while for partially accurate ones (accuracy = 0.5), 44% of sources were reliable. This method can offer sufficient evidence but requires human approval as the average accuracy is 0.52 across all HEIs. Examples of the limitations of this implementation are presented next, through examples of inconsistent answers across different HEIs.

The main limitation of the presented approach is that when relevant sources are not found, the tool still tries to answer by providing unrelated information. In most cases, if it doesn't find official HEI information relating to digital readiness, it references courses with similar keywords instead. This was showcased in the example of the answer regarding indicator D2.1 in section 3.1. This was also found in UPAT implementation for *D1.12 – Monitoring of Emerging Technologies* where false information was provided with unrelated sources about UPAT's activity with emerging technologies. From UVA implementation for *D1.13 – Monitoring Progress* where it was asked if UVA uses Key Performance Indicators to measure its digital transformation progress, the information it provided was a doctoral theses and course curriculum. In University of Duisburg-Essen implementation for *D2.9 – Develop a change management plan* where in the start stated that it didn't find search results regarding the question but continues to state "*there are indications that the university considers various aspects of change management in its degree programs and research projects*" were the information and none of the sources were relevant to the initial question. It is apparent that the LLM tool, relies more on common key terms between the question and the sources, than on understanding the nuanced differences between

related concepts, such as a university's digital transformation strategy and a course it offers on digital strategy.

To ensure accurate measurement, human evaluators should intervene to approve answers in this implementation. We investigated if reliability of cited sources could predict accuracy. Accurate answers typically had 70% reliable sources, partially accurate had 54%, and inaccurate had 25%. We tested this with a classification algorithm, but assumptions were only correct 46% of the time, underlining the necessity of human approval for LLM-generated answers.

As stated in section 2.3, for 19 indicators we can find reliable information. Based on the answers from the implementation, some can be measured using a binary scale, like the existence of documents or units. For the more complex indicators, we can create a 5-point Likert scale, like those regarding the HEI activities. Such as *D2.6 - Foster digital inclusion and accessibility*, which evaluates digital inclusion and accessibility based on factors like responsible units, support provided, and related seminars. The evaluator based on the actions listed in the answer can decide in what degree the HEI applies digital inclusion and accessibility.

5 Conclusions

We examined in this study if existing Large Language Model (LLM) tools could effectively assess key indicators relating to dimensions D1 (Digital Leadership and Governance) and D2 (Digital Strategy and Policies) of the Digiready+ Framework, which require qualitative data. Our research questions (RQs) were as follows: RQ1: Can LLM tools assess D1 and D2 indicators? RQ2: Do these models offer sufficient supporting evidence? RQ3: Can these indicators be quantified and integrated into an overall methodology for assessing digital readiness in Higher Education Institutions?

After evaluating various LLM tools, we chose *Perplexity.ai*, a search engine powered by LLM, and devised a methodology to generate appropriate question prompts for indicators of D1 and D2 where HEIs should have publicly available information. We applied this methodology across three European universities, UPAT, UDE, and UVA. We evaluated the accuracy of generated answers against ground truth and relevancy criteria.

For RQ1, we found that 14 out of 19 indicators across D1 and D2 could be measured, with an average accuracy of 0.65 using this approach. Concerning RQ2, we discovered that 60% of referenced sources in generated answers were relevant to the HEI and question, rising to 75% for the most accurate responses. In addressing RQ3, we proposed quantifying gathered information using yes/no or 5-point Likert scales, depending on the indicator. We emphasized the importance of human involvement in approving answers due to potential limitations in tool accuracy.

In conclusion, while LLM tools such as *Perplexity.ai* can aid measuring dimensions like D1 and D2, human supervision is still required in order to guarantee accuracy. This approach allows for the efficient assessment of digital readiness in HEIs while recognizing the nuanced nature of qualitative data evaluation.

Acknowledgements

The work presented here has been funded by Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union, and coordinated by IKY Hellenic Scholarships Foundation, Project number 2021-1-EL01-KA220-HED-000027521, Project partners are: The University of Patras, University of Valladolid, University of Duisburg-Essen, EDEN Digital Learning Europe, GUNet Greece. We would like to acknowledge Yasin Esiri and Ha Thuong Tran from the University of Duisburg-Essen (UDE) for their contribution to this research.

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